

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Reaction of short-duration rice varieties to leaf yellowing

M. Subramanian, A.P.M.K. Soundararaj, and V. Sivasubramanian, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

An unusual epidemic form of leaf yellowing associated with stunted growth in 1984 was identified as tungro virus in interaction with Fe toxicity and H₂S injury. Promising short-duration varieties were screened and rated for resistance to leaf yellowing and stunting: highly resistant, 0-10% affected; resistant, 11-25% affected; moderately resistant, 26-50% affected; susceptible, 51-75% affected; and highly susceptible, 100% affected.

Many of the Tamil Nadu and IET varieties were susceptible; IRRI varieties or cultures IR50, IR52, IR56, IR58, IR62, IR29725-3-1-3-2, IR29725-109-1-2-1, and Sri Lankan BG367-4

Resistance of short-duration rice varieties to leaf yellowing. Aduthurai, India.

Variety, cultivar	Rating
IR50, IR52, IR56, IR58, IR62, IR29725-3-1-3-2, IR29725-109-1-2-1, and BG367-4	Highly resistant
AD85001, ACM10, TNAU80058, TNAU801774, TNAU801803, TNAU801837, IR28, IR29, IR36, IR13429-150-3-2-1-2, IR14735-52-2-1, IR25924-51-2-3, IR29602-65-2-3, IET7985, and IET8715	Resistant
TKM9, PY3, TM4865, TNAU801790, TNAU801793, TNAU801798, TNAU801801, TNAU801824, TNAU801877, IR30, IR40, IR60, IR18348-36-3-3 (IR64), IR25571-31-1, IR28224-3-2-3-2, KAU1727, IET7984, IET7988, IET7989, IET8052, and IET9267	Moderately resistant
ADT36, AS688, TM8089, AD9246, TM4660, AS25370, AS13744, Cauvery, TNAU (AD) 103, TNAU801776, TNAU801786, TNAU801804, TNAU801807, TNAU801808, TNAU801838, TNAU801846, TNAU83023, TNAU83054, TNAU83068, TNAU83080, TNAU83081, TNAU83095, TNAU83106, TNAU83108, TNAU83113, UPR238-42-2-3, TCA1, UPR254-35-3-2, DPR34-2-1-2, IR9729-67-3, KAU2084, IET1722, IET5961, IET7625, IET7713, IET7721, IET8099, IET8114, IET8122, IET8649, IET8608, IET8893, IET9266, and IET9268	Susceptible
ADT31, Co 33, Co 37, Kannagi, AD24155, TNAU83079, TNAU801870, TNAU83025, TNAU83079, TNAU83082, TNAU83134, IET1444, IET4786, IET7569, IET7727, IET8098, IET8161, IET8191, and IET8686	Highly susceptible

were highly resistant (see table). Tamil Nadu entries AD85001, TNAU80058, TNAU801803, and ACM10 were

resistant. IRRI varieties IR30, IR40, IR60, and IR64 were moderately susceptible. ☞

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INSECT RESISTANCE

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) at flowering stage

K.S. Kushwaha and R. Singh, H.A.U. Rice Research Station, Kaul 132021, Kurukshetra, Haryana, India

Four fields with Jaya, PR106, and HKR101 transplanted during the first week of Jul 1985 and Pusa 33 transplanted during the last week, with recommended fertilizer, were evaluated for yield losses to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* attack at flowering. Three healthy and three hopperburned 5 × 4 m patches were harvested and threshed separately. Grain was sun-dried to equal moisture content.

Data showed significant yield losses (see table). ☞

Yield losses caused by whitebacked planthopper in tall and dwarf rice varieties.

Variety	Replication	Healthy patch		Hopperburned patch		Yield loss		
		Yield (t/ha)	Grain moisture (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain moisture (%)	t/ha	Average (t/ha)	Percent
Jaya	1	7.9	13.2	4.1	12.2	3.8	2.8	42.4
	2	5.9	12.7	3.6	11.7	2.3		
	3	6.0	13.0	3.7	11.1	2.3		
PR106	1	9.0	13.8	2.4	13.6	6.6	6.6	71.5
	2	9.2	13.9	2.2	13.7	7.0		
	3	9.5	13.8	3.4	13.4	6.1		
HKR101	1	8.5	13.6	1.7	12.5	6.8	6.7	79.8
	2	8.0	14.0	1.6	12.4	6.4		
	3	8.7	13.6	1.8	13.1	6.9		
Pusa 33	1	5.0	13.2	2.4	12.2	2.6	2.6	54.2
	2	4.3	12.9	2.0	12.3	2.3		
	3	5.0	13.3	2.0	12.1	3.0		
F Test		Sig. ***		Sig. ***				
S.E.M. ±		0.5		0.2				
CD (P = 0.05)		1.2		0.5				
CV %		0.8		1.6				